

KINETICS OF HALOGENATION OF FATTY ACIDS. PART II. BROMINATION OF ACETIC ACID*

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The kinetics of bromination of sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid has been measured at 35° and 45° in presence of excess of sodium bromide. The reaction is found to be bimolecular, the bimolecular constant k_2 having the mean value 1.90 litre/mole min⁻¹ at 35° and at bromide concentrations 0.109 to 0.168M.

The energy of activation is of the order of 15,600 cal./mole. The *PZ* factor has got almost the normal value of 10¹¹.

Using different alkali acetates, the speeds are found to be in the order : K > Na > Li.

Water strongly accelerates the reaction, the speed rising progressively with increasing proportions of water to a maximum, after which the speed falls off. In acetic acid containing about 50% or more of water, the bimolecular nature of the reaction is no longer evident. In pure water, practically no reaction is found to occur.

It is suggested that the reaction occurs through the attack of the positive end of the polarised bromine molecule on the α -carbon atom which becomes activated by an inductive mechanism.

In a previous paper (Das and Palit, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 322) we have reported the results obtained from a preliminary study of the reaction of iodine with sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid medium. It is reported therein, as also in an earlier note (Das, *Science & Culture*, 1948, 14, 165) that bromine too reacts with the same system and other similar systems, the reaction being much faster than with iodine. The present paper deals with the preliminary results of the kinetics of the bromination of sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid medium.

Bromine is practically without any action on saturated aliphatic acids at the ordinary temperature. Lapworth (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 30) reports that bromine scarcely acts on acetic acid even at its boiling point, and the reaction is catalysed by HCl or HBr. Watson (*ibid.*, 1925, 2067) studied the bromination of acetic, propionic and *n*-butyric acids at 100° in presence and absence of catalysts. The reaction is rather slow even at such a high temperature in absence of catalyst, and the course of the reaction is kinetically quite complex and difficult of elucidation and indicates autocatalysis by the HBr formed. The bromination is catalysed by HBr and HCl, the action of the halogen acids being specific and not involving any general acid-catalysis. Acetic anhydride, various acid chlorides and especially acid bromides, if added in excess of the water present in the acid, act as powerful catalysts at 100°. The reaction rate is proportional to the first power of the concentration of bromine as well as that of the catalyst. No base-catalysis has so far been reported for the bromination of aliphatic acids. On the contrary, Watson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 2458, 3065) observed that the bromination of acetic anhydride was strongly retarded by quinoline, and to a lesser extent, by sodium acetate. Other bases like pyridine, isoquinoline,

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aniline, and different aliphatic amines and NH_4 -acetate are less powerful inhibitors. The inhibitory action of sodium acetate is of particular interest to us, when viewed in the light of the reaction forming the subject of our present study.

EXPERIMENTAL

The methods of preparation of materials were similar to those described in our previous communication (*loc. cit.*). Experimental procedure for kinetic measurements was the same as described therein. Laboratory reagent bromine was used without any special purification. Acetate was estimated as follows. The acetic acid solution was evaporated on a water-bath, the residue taken up with glycol-isopropyl alcohol mixture and titrated with standard HClO_4 solution in the same mixed solvent, with thymol blue as indicator. This method, originally devised by one of the authors (Palit, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1946, 18, 246) has been found to be quite suitable for estimation of acetate (cf. Green, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1948, 37, 240).

Reaction Kinetics.—From our results to be reported the reaction appears to take the course,

In the first step, one acetate ion undergoes bromination, liberating a molecule of HBr , which being a strong acid neutralises a second acetate ion, the latter being a strong base in glacial acetic acid medium. Thus, with every molecule of bromine, two acetate ions take part in the overall reaction. The second step involving the neutralisation of a strong base with a strong acid is naturally an instantaneous process, so that the first step must be the rate determining factor. Now, the instantaneous rate of reaction is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_2[\text{Ac}][\text{Br}_2] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where x denotes the amount of Br_2 consumed. The tribromide equilibrium is defined by the equation,

$$K = \frac{[\text{Br}_2][\text{Br}^-]}{[\text{Br}_3^-]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Let a and b denote the initial concentrations of bromine and acetate respectively. Then, the total titratable bromine at any time t is given by

$$a - x = [\text{Br}_2] + [\text{Br}_3^-] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Combining equations (2) and (3), the concentration of free bromine at any time t is given by

$$[\text{Br}_2] = \frac{(a-x)K}{K + [\text{Br}^-]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Now, the total bromide at any stage is given by $x = [\text{Br}^-] + [\text{Br}_3^-]$ (5)

Combining this equation with (2) and (4) and solving the resulting quadratic equation, the concentration of free bromide at any state is given by

$$[\text{Br}^-] = \frac{2x - a - K + \sqrt{(-2x + a + K)^2 + 4Kx}}{2} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Substituting this value of $[\text{Br}^-]$ in (4), we may obtain the concentration of free bromine at any stage of the reaction.

Thus, the kinetic equation (1) assumes the form

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k_2 (b - 2x) (a - x) K}{K + [\text{Br}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where $[\text{Br}^-]$ has got the value given by equation (6) and K is the equilibrium constant given by equation (2). This equation, however, involves enormous calculations which can be simplified to a great extent by carrying out the reaction in presence of bromide added in excess (cf. Griffith and Mackown, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1932, 28, 752; Nozaki and Ogg, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942 64, 697). If c represents the concentration of added bromide, it can be shown that free bromide at any stage is given by

$$[\text{Br}^-] = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (c + 2x - a - K) + \sqrt{(-c - 2x + a + K)^2 + 4K(c + x)} \right\} \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

Now, if x is small in comparison with c , from the above equation it may be seen that $[\text{Br}^-]$ remains practically constant throughout the reaction. Hence, free bromine at any instant is given by equation (4) as

$$[\text{Br}_2] = \frac{(a - x)K}{K + [\text{Br}^-]} = \alpha (a - x) \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

where α is a constant because $[\text{Br}^-]$ is constant under the conditions of experiment, i. e., at any instant is proportional to the total titratable bromine present. Under these conditions equation (7) assumes the form

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \alpha k_2 (b - 2x) (a - x) \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

When $b = 2a$, this being the case in most of our experiments, the above equation reduces to the form

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = 2\alpha k_2 (a - x)^2 \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

On integration we have,

$$\frac{1}{a - x} = 2\alpha k_2 t + c' \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

Thus, the reciprocal of the total bromine concentration, when plotted against t , will give a straight line, the slope of which is $2\alpha k_2$, and hence the bimolecular constant k_2 may be calculated. Experimental results were found to be in excellent agreement with this equation. The straight lines so obtained do not, however, pass through the zero time point. Some of the typical results are represented (Fig. 1) and the corresponding data in the following tables.

FIG. 1

The figures on the curves refer to respective expt. Nos. as represented in the relevant tables. Ordinates for the curves 1-5 are shown on the left and those for 16 and 17 on the right.

Tribromide Equilibrium in Glacial Acetic Acid.—As would be seen from above, a knowledge of the tribromide equilibrium constant in glacial acetic acid (K) is essential to interpret the kinetic data. This was studied by Nozaki and Ogg (*loc. cit.*) and they have given a series of values for K at different temperatures and ionic strengths. From these data we have calculated the values of K at 35° and 25° by the application of Van't Hoff's equation, the validity of which for this particular case was also demonstrated by the same workers (*loc. cit.*). The values of K at ionic strength, close to our experimental conditions thus obtained, are given below and have been utilised in our calculations.

$$K_{35}^\circ = 2.2 \times 10^{-2}$$

$$K_{25}^\circ = 1.49 \times 10^{-2}$$

TABLE I

Change of thiosulphate titre (N/100) in c. c. for 5 c. c. of reaction mixture.

Temp. = 35°. Initial conc. of bromine (a) = 0.0125M. Initial conc. of Na acetate (b) = 0.035M. Concentration of added bromide (c) is given for each run at the head of the corresponding column in moles/litre.

	Experiment number				
	1	2	3	4	5
	c = 0.168	0.153	0.138	0.123	0.109
Time.	Titre	Titre	Titre	Titre	Titre.
0 min.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.
10	11.20	10.82	11.02	10.92	—
20	10.56	10.50	10.18	10.14	10.10
30	10.04	9.98	9.80	9.54	9.20
40	9.66	9.42	9.24	9.02	8.52
50	9.24	8.92	8.76	8.60	8.10
60	8.86	8.66	8.34	8.12	7.68
90	7.90	7.66	7.32	7.10	6.62
120	7.20	7.02	6.64	—	—

The Bimolecular Constant.—(On carrying out the reaction at different concentrations of bromide running up to 0.26M, the values of k_2 , calculated as above, were found to lie in the range 1.41—2.28 (litre/mole) min^{-1} units at 35°. This divergence in the values obtained might be due to the variable amounts of water likely to be associated with the different samples of acetic acid used in the experiments, as water strongly accelerates the reaction. Using a highly purified sample of acetic acid, the data shown in Table I were obtained, and the determination of k_2 from these results gave the following values, which are found to be fairly concordant and independent of bromide concentration.

TABLE II

Values of the bimolecular constant (k_2) at 35°.

Expt. No.	Conc. of bromide.	ak_2 .	k_2 (litre/mole) min^{-1} .	Mean value of k_2
1	0.168M	0.222	1.85	1.90
2	0.153	0.244	1.88	
3	0.138	0.281	1.94	
4	0.123	0.304	1.92	
5	0.109	0.333	1.91	

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Effect of Temperature.—The reaction was studied at 35° and 25° in presence of similar concentrations of bromide. At the lower temperature, there is an apparent period of induction, as noticed in the case of iodination as well. The reason for this is not understood. From the value of the ratio k_{35}/k_{25} , the activation energy was calculated and found to be of the order of 15,600 cal. This may be compared with the value of 25,000 cal. obtained for iodination. In Table III are given the results of two typical runs at 25°, together with two runs at 35°, for comparison. Values of k_p at 25° are found to be 0.94—1.00 (litre/mole) min⁻¹ units. The *PZ* factor calculated from these results is found to be of the order of 10¹¹, which appears to be almost a normal value.

TABLE III
Effect of temperature.

		Experiment No.			
		6	7	8	9
		35°	Temperature 25°	35°	25°
<i>a</i> = 0.025 <i>M</i>			0.0238 <i>M</i>	0.0125 <i>M</i>	0.0125 <i>M</i>
<i>b</i> = 0.05			0.05	0.025	0.025
<i>c</i> = 0.260			0.260	0.133	0.097
Time.	Titre	Titre	Titre	Titre	Titre
0 min.	25.00 c.c.	23.80 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	
10	21.58	—	11.70	—	
20	19.80	21.75	10.85	12.40	
30	18.22	21.40	10.20	12.06	
45	16.48	20.35	9.25	11.44	
60	15.20	19.35	8.30	11.04	
75	—	18.70	—	—	
90	13.02	18.10	7.30	10.00	
105	—	17.35	—	—	
120	11.72	16.80	6.50	9.54	

Effect of Different Alkali Acetates.—The reaction was also carried out with potassium and lithium acetates to compare the effects of the different alkali metals. Due to the very sparing solubility of potassium bromide in glacial acetic acid, the reaction was studied for all the three alkali acetates, in absence of any added bromide (Table IV). The speeds were found to lie in the order: K > Na > Li. The difference between Na and Li, however, is not so pronounced. An exactly similar effect was observed by us for the corresponding reactions with iodine. This order, as reported earlier, is also the order of the conductivities of these salts in glacial acetic acid medium (Kolthoff and Wiliman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1014).

TABLE IV

Effect of different alkali metals.

Temp. = 35°. Change of thiosulphate titre with time. $a = [\text{Br}_2] = 0.0125M$,
 $b = [\text{Ac}] = 0.025M$.

Time.	Experiment No.		
	10	11	12
	K.	Alkali metal Na.	Li.
	Titre	Titre	Titre
0 min.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.
5	9.60	10.80	10.60
10	8.45	9.90	10.00
20	7.15	8.80	9.15
30	6.25	8.10	8.50
45	5.50	7.20	7.90
60	5.00	6.70	7.35

Effect of Water.—Water strongly accelerates the reaction and the speed rapidly increases with increasing proportions of water. In Table V are shown some typical results obtained in aqueous acetic acid media containing varying proportions of water in presence and absence of bromides.

TABLE V

Effect of water.

Temp. = 35°.

Experiment No.

Time.	Water contents in acetic acid (% by volume).				
	0%	10%	50%	8%	20%
	$a = 0.0125M$	$0.0125M$	$0.0125M$	$0.0096M$	$0.0096M$
	$b = 0.0125$	0.0125	0.025	0.0192	0.0192
	$c = \text{Nil}$	Nil	Nil	0.201	0.201
	Titre	Titre	Titre	Titre	Titre
0 min.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	12.50 c.c.	9.63 c.c.	9.63 c.c.
5	11.18	9.52	3.60	—	—
10	10.40	8.50	2.12	8.75	7.66
20	9.20	7.68	—	7.90	6.10
30	8.78	7.12	—	7.40	5.30
45	8.20	6.80	0.45	6.70	4.34
60	8.00	6.52	—	6.16	3.70
90	6.50	6.12	—	5.30	2.76
120	—	5.82	—	4.66	—

In pure aqueous medium, as also in 5% aqueous acetic acid, very little reaction is found to occur. In acetic acid containing about 50% or higher proportion of water, the bimolecular nature of the reaction (in presence of excess bromide) is no longer evident, and no mathematical relationship could be found out to represent the kinetic results. The kinetics of the reaction in such aqueous acetic acid media are still under investigation.

The reaction was followed kinetically at 35° in acetic acid containing 8% and 20% water respectively at 0.201*M* bromide concentration (Table V; Expt. No. 16 & 17), and the values of ak_2 were found out graphically as before (Fig. 1; curves 16 and 17). To determine k_2 , the values of the tribromide equilibrium constant (K) in the different media are necessary. From the values of K_{11} , given by Jones (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 88, 392) for aqueous acetic acid media, it is found that K does not change enormously, unless the water content is very high. Assuming a similar effect to occur at 35°, the values of K_{11} were roughly calculated for aqueous acetic acid containing 8% and 20% water. The approximate values of k_2 were then calculated on this basis, which are tabulated below (Table VI).

TABLE VI

Values of k_2 in aqueous acetic acid.

Expt. No.	% Water in acetic acid (by volume).	K (approx.).	ak_2 .	k_2 (approx.) (litre/mole) min ⁻¹ .
16	8	0.027	0.437	3.6
17	20	0.035	1.36	8.5

The accelerating effect of water is, in part, due to an increase in the value of K in aqueous acetic acid media, implying a higher concentration of free Br_2 , but this factor is too small to account for the enhanced speed, as evident from the above table.

The higher speed of the reaction in water might be thought to arise from a greater dissociation of the acetate caused by the addition of water, but this is not the whole story as shown by the fact that practically no reaction occurs in pure water. It is interesting to note in this connection that bromine is found to react very slowly with aqueous acetic acid containing 8 to 20 % water even in absence of any added acetate.

Bromination and Iodination compared.—The two reactions present many points of similarity between themselves. Both the reactions are kinetically bimolecular, but bromination is more than hundred times faster than the reaction with iodine. Both reactions are accelerated by water and the relative effects of different alkali metals are also similar in both the cases. The most important difference between the two reactions, however, lies in the fact that whereas bromination goes to completion, in iodination, an apparent state of equilibrium is attained where the greater part of iodine remains unchanged. Thus, using even a molar concentration of acetate with as low as 0.0125*M* iodine, the reaction proceeds less than half-way. In bromination, on the other hand, with the same concentration (0.0125*M*) of the halogen, 0.025*M* acetate is sufficient to carry the reaction to completion in less than 96 hours. With higher con-

centrations of acetate, the reaction is naturally complete in a shorter period. Thus, no back-reaction being involved here, the reaction with bromine, unlike that with iodine, is more amenable to a critical kinetic study.

There is another important point to note in connection with the bromination reaction. According to the course of the reaction proposed by us, for each molecule of bromine, two molecules of sodium acetate take part in the overall reaction. Hence, if we start with equimolecular proportions of both the reactants, only half of the bromine should be consumed. In fact, about half the bromine was found to react in course of a few hours. But, on keeping the reaction mixture for several days, the reaction was found to proceed fairly beyond the half-value stage. This is presumably due to further bromination of the monobromoacetate first formed, the speed of which must be very slow with respect to that of the primary reaction, as otherwise we would not have obtained such consistent straight lines as previously reported (Fig. 1).

It may be mentioned in this connection, that various workers have studied the kinetics of many reactions involving bromine and iodine, in presence of acetate buffers and also using acetate as a catalyst (Bell and Lidwell, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1940, A, 176, 88; Pederson, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, 38, 601, 999; Nozaki and Ogg, *loc. cit.* Dawson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2282; 1928, 2844; 1929, 1884, etc.). These reactions were carried out in different media like water, glacial acetic acid and also aqueous acetic acid. No account was, however, taken of any reaction that might occur between the halogen and the acetate added, and naturally there is every reason to be sceptic about the reliability of the results obtained by them. The reaction of the acetate with iodine is very slow and may introduce only a small error, but with bromine in glacial as well as in aqueous acetic acid medium the reaction is fairly fast, faster than many of the common bromination reactions, and hence, the discrepancy likely to be associated with their results can hardly be ignored as negligible.

Mechanism.—Carbonyl compounds are, in general, easily susceptible to halogen substitution, and the reaction usually proceeds through a tautomeric mechanism. This typical property of the carbonyl group is, however, absent in free carboxylic acids, due to structural differences, which we have discussed in our previous paper. Silver, mercury and thallium salts of carboxylic acids are known to react with halogens giving alkyl or aryl halides, esters and carbon dioxide, and the reaction is said to proceed through the formation of an intermediate complex of the nature of a pseudohalogen (Kleinberg, *Chem. Rev.*, 1947, 40, 381; Hunsdiecker *et al.*, *Chem. Abstracts*, 1940, 34, 1685). α -Bromo-esters have been prepared by the action of bromine on potassium salts of half-esters of dicarboxylic acids (Dice and Bowden, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 3107). But in all such cases, which are attended with simultaneous substitution and decarboxylation, the reactions are quite complex and can hardly be represented by any simple mechanism.

In the present case, we have definitely established the bimolecular nature of the reaction, which clearly points out that sodium acetate is the active reactant, undergoing direct bromine substitution. In a medium of such low dielectric constant as acetic acid, sodium acetate is only incompletely dissociated and exists as ion-pairs, most probably solvated (Kolthoff and Wiliman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1007). The

reactivity of the acetate towards bromine, as against the relative inactivity of free acetic acid, can be explained by a mechanism involving sodium acetate ion-pairs and polarised bromine molecule (cf. Das and Palit, *loc. cit.*). The failure of the reaction in aqueous medium clearly suggests that acetic acid molecules have also got something to do in the matter, probably by way of solvation. In substitution reactions, bromine behaves as an electrophilic reagent and the reaction is facilitated by a high electron density at the point of attack. In the acetate ion, there is a concentration of negative charge on the α -carbon atom due to the influence of the negatively charged oxygen, and this leads to substitution. The reaction possibly occurs through the formation of an activated complex of the type shown below :

It must be distinctly understood, however, that in the mechanism suggested above, bromine is supposed to act *not* through the formation of any free Br^+ cation, but merely as an inductively *polarised* molecule. Free bromine cation is known to exist, in appreciable concentration, only in an aqueous solution of HOBr in presence of mineral acids (Derbyshire and Waters, *Nature*, 1949, 164, 447; Weiss, *Ann. Reports*, 1947, 44, 79). In most of the reactions with bromine, however, a mechanism involving free Br^+ cation is inadmissible, as that would imply a specific reaction rate in excess of the collision frequency of this ion with the substance undergoing bromination (Bartlett and Tarbell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 466).

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